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on

DOUBLING FARMERS INCOME FOR SUSTAINABLE & HARMONIOUS AGRICULTURE
'DISHA-2021' @ Sambodhi Retreat, Dhanbad, Jharkhand

ABSTRACTS PROCEEDINGS BOOK

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Dr. SANJEEW KUMAR SINHA

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Chief Editor

Dr. SANJEEW KUMAR SINHA

Assistant professor-cum-Scientist, Soil Science, SRI, Dr.Rajendra Prasad central Agricultural University,
Pusa, Samastipur-848125

Editors

Dr. SHANTI BHUSHAN

Jr. Scientist-cum-Asstt. Professor
Veer Kunwar Singh Agricultural College, Near Idgah, P.O. Dumraon Textiles
Dumraon 802 136, Buxar, Bihar, India, Patna 800 001

Dr. R. S. SINGH

Tirhut College of Agriculture, Dholi, Muzaffarpur , (Under RPCAU, Pusa, Samastipur)

Dr. ANIL KUMAR

(Assitant Professor cum Junior Scientist, Department of Plant Breeding & Genetics, Bihar Agricultural
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Dr. EKHLAQUE AHMAD

Junior Scientist-cum-Asstt. Prof., Zonal Research Station, Birsa Agricultural University, Chianki, Palamau

Dr. ARCHANA KUSHWAHA

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Dr. RAVI RANJAN KUMAR

(Assitant Professor cum Junior Scientist, Department of Molecular Biology and Geenetic Engineering,
Bihar Agricultural University, Sabour, Bhgalpur, Bihar-813210)

Er. B K YADAV

Scientist (Agril. Engg.) KVK, Balumath Latehar, BAU, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

Dr. JAI KUMAR

Assistant Professor-cum- Junior Scientist, Department of Forest Products & Utilization, Faculty of
Forestry, BAU, Kanke, Ranchi (Jharkhand)

Dr. AMARENDRA KUMAR

BAU, Sabour, Bhagalpur, Bihar

Er. SATISH KUMAR

(BAU, Sabour, Bhagalpur, Bihar)

&

Dr. BRAJENDRA

Principal Scientist, ICAR-Indian Institute of Rice Research, Hyderabad

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SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS FOR DOUBLING FARMERS' INCOME

Adarsh S.^{1*}, Ameena M.²

^{1,2}Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Kerala Agricultural University

*Correspondence author email: sssadarshsss@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Income is said as money received, especially on a regular basis for the works done or through investments. The impressive agricultural growth and gains since 1947 stand as a tribute to the farmers' resilience to multiple challenges. Development of the agriculture sector in India has focused primarily on raising agricultural output and improving food security. Fluctuating farm income is causing detrimental effect on the interest in the farming and farm investments, and forces cultivators, to leave farming. In this background the goal is set to double the farmers income by 2022-23 for the welfare of farming community. The pathway to double farmers' income includes strategies for accelerated growth, post-production interventions, agricultural marketing, resource use efficiency, production enhancement through productivity gains, secondary agriculture, risk management, empowering the farmers through extension & knowledge diffusion, using science for doubling farmers' income and using governance framework to recommend and implement the policies. At present, the proven methods which ensure a non-fluctuating double in farmers income are the sustainable crop and soil management practices. Zero tillage, raised bed planting, mulching, aerobic rice cultivation, rain water harvesting, precision-based drip irrigation, mechanisation of deep placement of urea, sequential intercropping, soil specific nutrient management, use of mobile applications (Phule Jal), variable rate of fertilizer application through Green Seeker, fertiliser applied as briquettes, etc. have given fruitful results of improving farmers' profit. The sources of future growth in improving farmers' income need demand driven logistics system, improved and optimised input delivery mechanism, institutional credit support, marketing intelligence system, periodic agricultural risk assessment and focus on sustainable efficiency.

Keywords: Income; Farmer; Profit; Economics